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GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Institutional assessment process checklist

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

This checklist is meant to be used during an overall research assessment process of an organization or institution often referred to as Research Assessment Exercise, RAE. Based on the Dutch [Strategy Evaluation Protocol \(SEP\) 2021-2027](#), created by NOW (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek), KNAW (Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen) and UNL (Universiteiten van Nederland, Hague), March 2020, the checklist is still applicable and editable to fit circumstances and terminology of different countries and different kinds of research organisations.

The checklist has questions that support documentation and follow up of all necessary stages of an assessment process, and duties by the key actors which in Dutch protocol are executive board, research unit to be assessed and impartial assessment committee.

The person responsible for filling out this form is usually the person who, on behalf of their position in the organization, is responsible for the overall research assessment process. Filling out together with other key persons participating in the research assessment process is recommended.

An essential condition for understanding and using this document is to familiarize yourself with the SEP protocol before starting an assessment process. **The main goal of SEP evaluation is to evaluate a research unit in light of its own aims and strategy.** An assessment committee of independent experts assesses the performance of the unit based on the self-evaluation and a site visit. The Dutch protocol pays attention to criteria such as research quality, the societal relevance and the viability of the unit, and aspects such as open science, academic culture, human resources policy and PhD policy.

Checklist as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this checklist supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This resource is most relevant for stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Instructions for filling the strategy self-evaluation form

The person responsible for filling out the form is usually the person who, on behalf of their position in the organization, is responsible for the overall research assessment process. Filling out the form together with other key persons participating in the research assessment process is recommended.

The evaluation of a research unit is always a momentous process for research management, researchers and staff supporting research, and that is why careful implementation of the process is important.

Examine carefully the [SEP protocol](#) to get a deep understanding of the protocol for assessing research units like universities, departments or subunits. Familiarization with SEP is necessary to be able to answer the questions and understand the purposes of the questions. Answer the questions, and supplement with informative notes and add rows in the tables if needed. The template may have one or more questions on the same subject to ensure the implementation of all stages of the process.

Essential actors in the Dutch protocol are executive board, research unit to be assessed and impartial expert assessment committee. Relevant issues in the Dutch protocol are aim and strategy of the unit to be assessed, strategic planning discussion and terms of references for assessment.

Names and terms used for actors and issues, and schedule of the evaluation process may vary from organisation to organisation and country to country and depending on the scope and context of the evaluation process as well as size of the unit or entity to be assessed. A detailed schedule of action for the research unit and assessment committee in the Dutch protocol is presented in Appendix A of the [SEP protocol](#) starting from page 28.

By customizing and applying this form to meet the needs of your organization, you can get the most out of it.

Information about actors

Unit to be assessed

Background details of the unit to be assessed determined by the executive board

Name of the unit	
Director of the unit	
Date when the unit was established	
Number of staff in the unit	
Staff structure in the unit	

Members of the executive board

Surname, first name	Position	Unit (faculty, department)

Add rows if needed

Impartial expert assessment committee

Title and name of the chair of the committee	Discipline	Nationality	Gender
Title and name of the independent secretary of the committee			
Title and name of the committee member			

Add rows if needed

Question	Yes	No
Is the composition of the assessment committee appropriately diverse in a broad sense?		

Aim and strategy of the unit to be assessed

Describe the aims and strategy of the unit to be assessed below.

The Dutch protocol pays attention to criteria such as research quality, the societal relevance and the viability of the unit, and aspects such as open science, academic culture, human resources policy and PhD policy.

Strategic planning discussions on the aims and strategy of the research unit

Question	Yes	No
Have strategic planning discussions between the executive board and research unit to be assessed been scheduled? In discussion the research unit shares its aspirations and ambitions as well as the strategy to attain them with the board.		

Schedule of the strategic planning discussions

Date of the planned strategic planning discussion	Was realized, yes	Not realized	New date

Terms of reference for assessment

Quantitative indicators chosen by the unit	Aims and issues of the strategy that are assessed by the indicators

Add rows if needed.

Describe the specific information about the research unit to be assessed and/or about elements that the assessment committee must consider.
Are there strategic recommendations for the entire discipline at the national level, in case of a nation-wide assessment covering a discipline?
What are the three assessment criteria and the four specific aspects? The Dutch protocol pays attention to criteria such as research quality, the societal relevance and the viability of the unit, and aspects such as open science, academic culture, human resources policy and PhD policy.
Has the executive board formulated and specified the terms of reference for assessment? Yes/No

Self-evaluation process, duties of the actors

Duties of the unit to be assessed

Question	Yes, date	No	Notes
Has the unit provided a narrative self-evaluation report reflecting the previous six years not exceeding 20 pages, excluding appendices and case studies?			
In the self-evaluation report, has the unit reflected its own research accomplishments and on its research discipline in general, as well as on the specific aspects, which e.g. in the Dutch protocol are open science, PhD policy and training, academic culture and human resources policy?			
Has the unit performed a SWOT analysis for the upcoming six-year period? E.g. aspects in the Dutch protocol are 1) open science, 2) PhD policy and training, 3) academic culture and 4) human resources policy			
Has the unit discussed the research unit's self-formulated aims and strategy in a series of strategic planning discussions with the board?			
Has the unit chosen quantitative indicators for which the unit should provide evidence, and based on the argument which it wants to develop?			
Has the unit organized a site visit during which the assessment committee can interview delegates from the unit and other relevant persons?			
Has the unit received an assessment report from the assessment committee for the correction of factual inaccuracies?			
Optional: Has the unit submitted a written response to the assessment report to the executive board?			

Duties of the executive board

Question	Yes. Date if relevant	No
Has the board ensured that all the research conducted within their institutions is assessed once every six years? Note: assessing period may vary from country to country		
Has the board scheduled the assessment process?		
Has the board determined the units to be assessed?		

Has the board appointed an impartial expert assessment committee?		
Has the board received a narrative self-evaluation report, SWOT-analysis and suggestions for indicators from the unit to be assessed?		
Has the board participated in strategic planning discussions where the research unit shares its aspirations and ambitions as well as the strategy to attain them with the board?		
Has the board specified the term of reference for the assessment committee?		
Has the board sent out the relevant documents to the assessment committee preferably at least four weeks but preferably eight weeks prior to the site visit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SEP • the terms of reference • the composition of the assessment committee and its secretary • the form for the statement of impartiality and the self-evaluation report 		
Has the board received the final assessment report formulated by the assessment committee?		
Has the board received a written response to the assessment report from the research unit assessed?		
Has the board responded to the report of the assessment committee?		
Has the board produced a position document in which it reflects on the assessment and states how it will follow up on the outcome of the assessment?		

Duties of the assessment committee

Question	Yes. Date if relevant	No
Has the assessment committee received following documents from the executive board at least four weeks prior to site visit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEP • terms of reference • composition of the assessment committee and its secretary • draft or final schedule of the site visits • the form of statement of impartiality 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the self-evaluation report? 		
Prior to the site visit, have the members of the assessment committee and the secretary signed a statement of impartiality?		
Has the assessment committee formulated an assessment report of the research unit in light of its aims and strategy, based on the self-evaluation and the site visit?		
Does the assessment report contain expert assessment of the research quality, the societal relevance and viability of the unit?		
Has the assessment committee reflected specific aspects which in the Dutch protocol are open science, PhD policy and training, academic culture and human resources policy		
Does the assessment report include suggestions and recommendations as to where and how improvements are envisaged?		
Has the assessment report been sent to the research unit to be assessed for the correction of factual inaccuracies?		
Has the assessment committee ensured that factual inaccuracies detected by the unit to be assessed are corrected?		

Duties by the secretary of the assessment committee

Question	Yes	No
Has the secretary remunerated for the time spent on the assessment, including travel expenses and lodging compensation when appropriate, according to the applicable rules of the institution?		
Has the secretary assisted the committee in interpreting and applying the SEP protocol as well as the terms of reference with regard to the research unit.		

After the assessment

Question	Yes, date	No
Have the unit´s self-evaluation report including case studies, the assessment report and executive board´s response to the report, position document, made publicly available within six months of the site visit?		
Have the executive board and research unit to be assessed discussed the assessment outcome and potential actions as part of quality assurance cycle?		
How will the assessment report be used in the quality assurance cycle?		

References

International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report.
<https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

VSNU KNAW NWO (2020) Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) for 2021-2027. March 2020, available in https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/documents/SEP_2021-2027.pdf, cited 15.1.2024

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